

BASICS OF PHYSICAL FITNESS, GENERAL AND SPECIAL FEATURES OF PREPARATION

Ismatov Po'latjon Abdumannobovich

Associate professor of Andijan State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8379512>

Annotation: in this article, the concept of physical training includes information about its main purpose, its importance in social life and in the activities of the engaged, methods, tools, the functions of general and special physical training, its specific features in physical development.

Keywords: Physical, preparation, health, engaged, general and special, organism, attributes, activity, functional, exercise, development.

The concept of physical fitness, social labor and all activities in the health system are aimed at creating a healthy lifestyle of the population, increasing their ability to work and living healthy. It is important that a person is able to stay healthy and maintain performance for many years due to his health. For this reason, great attention is paid to physical education and sports in order to strengthen the health of people, improve their working abilities and improve labor efficiency.

The adoption of decrees by the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan is important to improve the health of the population, ensure the physical perfection of students and youth, and to attract working workers and servants and intellectuals to the regular practice of physical education and sports. The main goal of popularizing physical education and sports among the population in the country is to ensure that people are always healthy, get used to physical education from childhood, mobilize youth for sports, participate in the world sports fields of athletes and, having achieved achievements, spread the fame of Uzbekistan in the world. On the other hand, the current era has been a result of technical progress, causing many to sit and work and make little effort. This, in turn, causes the circulatory system to suffer from acute depression, which is hypodynamia. Thirdly, there is an increase in the incidence of smallpox through tobacco smoking, "tasting" various herbs and alcohol, various infectious diseases (types of influenza), as well as various similar adverse conditions. The basis of the most important problems highlighted above is the deep absorption of socio-educational processes such as physical education, physical development and physical training.

The concept of physical fitness is such that these are active actions in the fact that every person, especially workers-servants of the mental and physical sphere and students-young people, are fit for any Labor (ability), physically strong, satisfied. Such practical activities are formed and strengthened only by physical labor and exercise. People with the disease perceive it well. The great alloma Abu Ali Ibn Sina places physical exercise (badantarbia) above any medication in health and strengthening it. When thinking about human health, of course, it will be necessary to constantly maintain it, develop it at the opportunity level. In this case, it is necessary that physical fitness is the most priority event. The age, gender and physical condition (sick or healthy) of those who are engaged in physical training are taken

into account, above all. On this basis, the range, amount and methods of execution of the given (performed) exercises are determined. As noted, the scope of training, which is carried out depending on the age, gender and physical condition of those involved, is extremely wide. Each of them is a separate topic. For this reason, we will dwell only on the general and special features of physical fitness.

Physical fitness: the main goal of physical fitness is the comprehensive development of the student (engaged), increasing his functional capabilities and strengthening his health.

It should be noted that the physical qualities of a person are closely related, and it is wrong to apply exercises to develop a certain quality. Meanwhile, exercise has a positive effect on the physical development of the student. Between general physical training tools, exercises performed on barriers, brusses, with various dumbbells are more effective for physical development. These exercises ensure body harmony. A complex of physical exercises aimed at creating muscle mass, a beautiful figure, improving external breathing, will preserve and strengthen youth health. To improve overall fitness, it is necessary to increase the number of exercises aimed at developing strength capabilities. For example, when performing to increase the circumference of the chest, pull-ups, roll-ups, touching the hanging lower legs to the fence, etc.k. exercises are performed. General physical fitness is one of the important components of practical training in increasing the physical fitness of a student. In this it is necessary to have a process aimed at developing physical qualities - strength, endurance, flexibility, agility and agility. The fact that general physical fitness exercises are at a high level serves as the basis for an increase in the effectiveness of training processes. General physical fitness includes a diverse set of tools. Including sports equipment and exercises performed with them, as well as other sports (acrobatics, athletics, sports games, swimming, etc.k.) are performed on the basis of general developmental exercises derived from. The concept of general physical fitness is that it is active actions in the fact that students are physically fit for any Labor (the development of qualities). Such practical activities arise only by performing physical exercises and are strengthened through it. And in order to have physical qualities, it is necessary to always engage in physical education and sports. In order for students to have physical qualities, general secondary schools cannot ensure that physical education (2 hours a week) classes are maintained throughout the week. Therefore, we need to teach students that in order for them to have physical training, it is necessary to diligently engage in physical education every morning and evening. The main way of physical fitness of students is participation in sports clubs, which are carried out outside the lesson (2-3 times a week). In place of the conclusion, it should be noted that in the process of physical training, through goal-oriented activities, as in other areas of physical and functional training, the planned result cannot always be achieved.

References:

- 1.Mahkamdjanov K.M. Jismoniy madaniyat nazariyasi va metodikasi Toshkent., darslik "Iqtisod - moliya" 2008-yil.
- 2.Salomov R.S. Sport mashg'ulotning nazariy asoslari -Toshkent., O'quv qo'llanma O'zDJTI, 2005-yil.
- 3.Юнусова Ф.Ю. Теория и методика физической воспитания. Учебное пособие. Ташкент. УзГосУФК. 2007 г.

4.Goncharova O.V. Yosh sportchilarning jismoniy qobiliyatlarini rivojlantirish. o'quv
qo'llanma, Toshkent., O'z DJTI, 2005-yil

5.David C. Watt Sports management and administration © 1998 David C. Wat

